

UTILIZATION OF TIERED- BASED MODULAR INSTRUCTION AND THE AQUACULTURE SKILLS OF GRADE 10 TECHNICAL VOCATIONAL EDUCATION STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study entitled “Utilization of Tiered- Based Modular Instruction and the Aquaculture Skills of Grade 10 Technical Vocational Students” aimed to determine the students’ perceptions on the utilization of tiered-based modular instruction and its relationship to the aquaculture skills of the learners through the use and analysis of self-made questionnaire and pre- and post-test results. The respondents of the study were the 31 Grade 10 students in Aquaculture during the school year 2020- 2021 at Tanauan School of Fisheries. They are assessed according to their first quarter grades or performances and classified according to their capacity namely: challenged, average, and advance learners. The study utilized survey questionnaire and pre and post-test to gather the data needed in the research and been sent thru their group chats using Google forms link. These instruments were validated first by experts in the field of Aquaculture before being utilized by the respondents. Findings revealed that there is a significant increase in the pre-test and post-test scores of the student- respondents in terms of their aquaculture skills after the utilization of the tiered-based modular instruction. The hypothesis stating that there is no significant increase in the level of performance of the students after the utilization of tiered- based modular instruction were now not sustained. And after all the data gathered and calculated, the result reveals that there is no significant relationship between the respondents- related variable and their aquaculture skills. The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the respondents’ related variable and the aquaculture skills of students were supported by evidences and therefore sustained. On the other hand, the result also shows that the perception of the student- respondents in the utilization of tiered- based modular instruction and their aquaculture skills were not significantly related to each other. Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the respondent’s perception on Tiered- Based Modular Instruction and Aquaculture skills of students is also sustained. It revealed that when the independent and dependent variables were computed against 0.01 level and 0.05 level of significance, the result showed that they were not significantly related with each other.

Keywords: Tiered- based modular instruction, aquaculture skills, Aquaculture